

TWO SINGHALESE INSCRIPTIONS.

BY B. GUNASEKARA.

No. 1.

AT THE RUWANWĒLI DA'GABA.

The translator has not had an opportunity of seeing this Inscription. The translation is made from a photograph* taken by Capt. Hogg, R.E., for the Ceylon Government.

With regard to the language it may be remarked that, with a few exceptions, it differs little from the modern, but the change is greater in the letters themselves. The translator would propose some new readings of the text and correct a few orthographical errors, noticing words which are rare, or nearly obsolete, in modern Sinhalese.

The Queen Lílávatí referred to in the Inscription, was the wife of Kírti Nissanka of the Kálinga dynasty. According to the Maháwaṅsa, she ascended the throne in the year 1753 of the Buddhist era, which corresponds with 1210 A. D., and reigned six years. She patronised Buddhism and caused two Vihára to be built, one at Parnasálaka, the site of the Lańkátílaka Vihára, and the other at Wĕligama.

INSCRIPTION.

අභයසලමේවත් කලාණවති සුවමිත්වහන්සෙව *a* දෙව
නු ඇසලපුර එකොලොස්වක් .. ද .. යා නකතින් සිරිසගබෝ
පුරක්කුමනොනු *b* | වනකුවති සුවමිත්වහන්සෙ *c* ඇතුළුවූ රජ
දරුවන්ගේ භඞාරපරිපාලනායකොට රත්නත්‍රයෙහි අඞිකපු
සාද *d* ඇති ශඞී *e* බුඞිගුණ | ත් සමමිත් රජපුසාද *f* රසින්
විරජමානවූ භඞාරපොතැ පිරිවතුබිම් විජයානාවන්හාමෙ

* No. 104. Pavement slab, 14·0 x 8·7, in front of S. Altar of the Ruwanwĕli Dágaba.

a සුවමිත්වහන්සෙව *b* පරකුමනොනු *c* සුවමිත් වහන්සේ
d අඞිකපුසාද *e* ශ්‍රඞා *f* රජපුසාද.

කුගේ අමුදු සුමෙ | ධාදෙවින්හා මෙකුන්ගේ බැන් ලංකාඅධි
 කාරකොට දනවු දෙවල්නාවන්හා වැන්දෙනලද අගමබර
 නොඑක් | පංචිනවරයන් *g* ගෙන් රුවන්මැලිසුවාමීන්ට දුටුගැ
 මුණු රජපුරුවන් ආදිවු නොඑක් | රජදරුවන්විසින් කරන
 ලද පුජා විශෙෂ අසා ප්‍රසාද පරවභවැ අනුන්හා අසාධාරණ
 පු | ඡ විශෙෂ යක් කලමැනවැසි නානාවිබවු අවදාස් අවසිය
 අසුවන් පමණ වස්තූයෙන් විගෙ | ඡවු කංචුකයක් බහා වූඩා
 මණ් ටවෙතා ප්‍රතිබිමබ *h* යක්සෙ ච්ශෙෂකොවැ සරහා පස්
 යාලනැ | මණසාලින් සොලොස්මටි(?)ලා අදවා ගනවපුපු
 සුගනධදිපයෙන් විවිතූකොවැ පානේගෙ | වැ(?)ධපපනාකා
 කදලිතොරණදින් විචිසරහා අනෙක වගීගයෙ කනදුසින්
 හා ස්ථිරපායාස | යෙන්හා මහොසයක්සෙ පලමුවනමඵවෙ
 හී නිරන්තරයෙන් සනියක් පුජකොවැ කපුරු දෙදසක් | ක
 ලදින් පානතුන්පනපිය වසා වේරියෙන් රියෙන් කබල්වලැ
 කපුරු පානපුදැ ගැ ඇතුළුවු නොඑක් .. ස් ප්‍රදිපපුජකරවා
 නොඑක් කමාන්ත කල මෙගෙ කල | වූන්ට අනට ගල්
 ඵබ්බුදුහා රන්පිලිහා උන්අමබුවන්ටද හදනාපිලිදි උනුසතු
 වූකරවා | විහාරඝෞචේ *i* සිවි ලියන්නවුන් සමදරුවන් වණ්
 ණකුවරුන් බමුණන් පසකුන් සිත්තරු | නටන්නන් ගිකියන්
 නන් බෙරගසන්නන් සකුන්දුරයන් පංචයන් පදෙනියෙ
 පගන් නහනග | නුන්දමාලෙබැලු මඟුල්මංචියන් මාලකා
 රන් ඔසනාවටුවන්ටන .. තට (?) ප්‍රසාදයෙන් රනින්ස | තුටු
 කරවා රුවන්මැලි මඵවෙදිමැ වූපවභ *j* අසා බමීකපීක
 යන්ට සුදුසු පුජකොට | වූපාරමසුවාමීන්ටන් ශ්‍රීමහාබොධින්
 වහන්සෙවන් කපුරු පහන්පනාකා පුජා ආදිවු නොඑක් | පුජා
 කරවා සත්ගෙණහී තෙරවරුන්වහන්සෙ ප්‍රධානකොවැ
 වස්තූවන්මහදන්හා සිවු | රුපිලිදි නැ නොනැනෙ සියලු
 ප්‍රත්‍යයන්ට පින්පෙන්දෙවා මෙ පුජාසු මහාජනයාටද න
 මාටද | බහුල ප්‍රීතිඋපදවා කලසු.....

TRANSCRIPT.

Abhayasalaméwan Kalyāṇawatī suwamínwahansēta¹ dewanu
 Esala pura ekoḷoswak .. da .. yá² nakatin Siri Sanga Bó Purakkra-
 ma Báhu³ | chakkrawarti suwámínwánse⁴ etuluwú rajadaruwangé
 bhaṇḍára paripálanayakoṭa ratnatrayehi adhikapprasáda⁵ eti

g පංචිනවරයන් *h* ප්‍රතිබිමබ *i* විහාරඝෞචේ *j* වූපවංස.

sardhá⁶ Buddhi guṇe | n samawit⁷ rájapprasáda⁸ rásín⁹ wirája-
 mánawú Bhaṇḍárapote Piriwatubím Wijayánáwan há mekugé
 amadu¹⁰ Sume | dhádevin há mekungé bēn Lanḡá Adhikára
 Koṭadanawu¹¹ Dewalnáwan¹² há ṭeṇ¹³ denalada ágamadhara
 noek¹⁴ | paṇḍita¹⁵ warayangen Ruwanmeḡi¹⁶ suwáminta¹⁷ Du-
 ṭugeṃunu rajjuruwan ádiwú noek | rajadaruwan visinkaranalada
 pújá wiṣeṣha asá prasáda parawaṣawe anun há asádháraṇa¹⁸
 pú | jáwiṣeshayak kaḡameṇaweḡi nánáwidhawú aṭadás aṭasiya asú-
 wakpamaṇa wastrayen wiṣe | shawú kaṇchukayak bahá chúdámaṇi
 chaitya pratibimbayak se wiṣeshakoṭe sarahá pasyálake |¹⁹
 maṇá sálin soḡosmaṭi (?)²⁰ lá andawá gandha pushpa sugandha
 dípayen wichitrakoṭe²¹ páné ge | ṭe (?) dhaja patáká kadali toraṇá-
 dín wíthi sarahá aneka warggaye kana deyin há kshírapáyasa | yen
 há mahoghayak se paḡamuwana maluwehi nirantarayen satiyak
 pújá koṭe kapuru dedásak | kalandin²² páta tun pana²³ piyawa
 sáwé²⁴ riyané riyané kabalwalekapuru pán puda²⁵ e | gé eṭuluwú
 noek .. s²⁶ pradípa pújá da karawá noek karmmánta kaḡa mehe
 kaḡa | wunṭa ataṭa gal ebú mundu há ran pilí há un ambuwanṭada
 handaná pilí dí unu²⁷ satuṭu karawá | wihárahásháwé²⁸ siṭi
 liyannawun samadaruwan²⁹ waṇṇakuwarun Bamuṇan pasakun³⁰
 sittaru | naṭannan gíkiyannan bera gasannan sakun durayan
 paṇchayan³¹ padeniye³² pané³³ nahana³⁴ ga | nun³⁵ da mále
 belú mangul miṇḍiyan³⁶ málákáran osanáwaṭuwantaṇa..nta (?)
 prasádayen raninsa | tuṭu karawá Ruwanmeḡi³⁷ maḡuwedíme Thú-
 pawanṣa asá dharmmakathikayanṭa sudusu pújákoṭa | Thúpárama³⁸
 swámintat śrī mahá bodhínwahansetaṭ kapuru pahan patáká
 pújá ádiwú noek | pújá karawá sat geṇehi terawarunwahanse
 pradhánakoṭe wasnéṭat³⁹ mahadan há siwu | ru pilí dí né noné
 ne siyalu pretayanṭa⁴⁰ pin pet⁴¹ dewá me pújá eṣú mahá
 janayáṭa da tamáṭa⁴² da | bahula prítí upadawá kaḡa pú.....⁴³

TRANSLATION.

Bhaṇḍárapote Piriwatubím Wijayánáwan, who carefully
 guarded the treasures of the Imperial Lord Siri Sanga Bó
 Purakkrama Báhu and other princes—who was highly pleased
 with the three gems—was endowed with faith and a clear

intellect, and was illumined with the rays of royal favour— (*this personage*) together with his mother Sumédhádévi and his nephew who held the offices of Adikárama of Lańká and Principal of the Koṭadanaw temple, having learned from many paṇḍits who were conversant with Buddhist literature and had offices conferred on them, what kind of offerings had been made to the venerable Ruwanmēli (*Dágaba*) by Duṭugemuṇu and many other princes, were transported with joy, and having resolved to make a grand offering superior to the offerings of others, encased (*the dágaba*) beautifully with about 8,880 cloths of various sorts : highly decorated it so as to look like the reflected image of a crown-jewel monument : caused mortar (*prepared*) from five yálas of good rice to be applied thereto : made it lovely with odoriferous flowers, scents, and lamps : adorned the streets with....., flags, banners, plantain-trees, triumphal arches, &c. : made on the first terrace offerings of various eatables and lumps of milk-rice constantly (*pouring in*) like a great flood during a week : honored it by lighting with 2,000 kalandas of camphor many thousands of lamps, inclusive of festoons of lamps and lamps of earthen vessels placed at intervals of one cubit on the third floral attar in the lower part of the dágaba : made presents of rings for the fingers set with stones, and of golden apparel for the different kinds of workmen and labourers : gave garments to their wives and rejoiced their hearts : and pleased with (*gifts of*) gold the writers, the overseers, the appraisers of property, Brahmins, cooks, painters, dancers, singers, tom-tom beaters, conch-blowers, players on the five kinds of musical instruments, ? persons who applied combs and unguents to the cavities (*in the dágaba*), the female servants with auspicious marks on them who took care of the terrace, florists, perfumers,..... Moreover having heard the Thúpawaṇsa (*the history of the dágabas*) while yet on the terrace of the Ruwanmēli Dágaba, they made suitable offerings to the clever preachers of Dharma, and honored the Thúpáráma and the illustrious and venerable Bó tree with many lamps lit with camphor, flags, &c. To the residents of the seven monastic establishments, amongst whom the priests were the foremost,

they gave much alms, and cloths for making yellow robes, (and) imparted the merit (*thus acquired*) to their kinsmen, strangers, and all the different kinds of Prétas, experiencing great joy themselves, while they caused the same to the mass of the people who heard of these offerings which were made under the asterism Visá on the 11th day of the bright half of Ēsala in the second year of Her Majesty Abhayasalaméwan Kalyána-watí.

completed by his brother Śeḍétissa. It is now known by the name of Rankot ('gold-pinnacled') Dágaba.

17. Read *svámīṅṭa* for *surámīṅṭa*.
18. *Anun há asádháraṇa*,—lit: 'not common with others,' 'unlike others,' i. e., 'surpassing others.'
19. *Yála* = 1,280 kuruni; 1 kuruniya being equal to 4 ṇeli.
20. Reading *selesmeṭi* for *soḷosmaṭi*, where *seles* may be derived from the Páli *silesa* 'union,' and *maṭi* (modern *meṭi*) from *mattiká* 'clay,' hence 'adhesive clay.'
21. The *ḡ* sound in *hoṭe* is now replaced by *a*.
22. *Kálanda* = 60 grains (Apothecaries' weight.)

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Reading “*Baṇḍárapotu* (1), *piriwatu* (2), *Bimvijayanáwan* (3) *há mekugé ambu Sumedhádévin há mekungé ben, &c.*,” the translation would run thus :—

“*Bimvijayanáwan* the younger brother of *Baṇḍárapotu* (who &c.....) and his wife *Sumedhádévi* and their son-in-law, who.....&c.”

1.—*Baṇḍárapotu* is perhaps the minister *Bhaṇḍárapustakí*, mentioned in *Maháwaṅso*, Part 2, Chap. 72, St. 215.

2.—*Pirivatu* = *paruvetri* (Sanskrit) “a younger brother married before his elder.”—Wilson.

8.—*Bimvijayanawan* = *Jagat (bhúmi, bim) vijayanaka*. Vide *Maháwaṅso*, Part 2, Chap. 77, St. 4.

auspicious marks on them who took care of the terrace, florists, perfumers,..... Moreover having heard the *Thúpawaṅsa* (*the history of the dágabas*) while yet on the terrace of the *Ruwanmeḷi Dágaba*, they made suitable offerings to the clever preachers of Dharma, and honored the *Thúpáráma* and the illustrious and venerable *Bó* tree with many lamps lit with camphor, flags, &c. To the residents of the seven monastic establishments, amongst whom the priests were the foremost,

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NOTES.

1. Read *svámīnwahanséta* for *suwamīnwahanseṭa*.
2. For *..da..yá* read *lada wisa*.
3. Read *Parákrama Báhu* for *Purakkrama Báhu*. The King here meant is Parákrama Báhu the Great of Polonnaruwa.
4. Read *Svámīnwahansé* for *suwámīnwānse*.
5. *Adhikapprasáda*,—omit the first *p*.
6. Read *ṣradhdhá* for *ṣardhá*.
7. *Samavit* = *sāmanvita*, the more common form in modern prose.
8. Omit the first *p* in *rājapprasáda*.
9. Reading *raṣṣin* or *raṣṣin* for *rásin*.
10. *Amadu* = the modern *ammandi*; the *du* in *amadu* is a suffix used to express endearment or familiarity and is another form of the modern *dē* which occurs in such words as *mēniyandē* 'mother,' *piyānandē* 'father,' &c.
11. *Kotadanawu*—supposed to be in Bintenna,
12. *Devalāwan* = *Dēwālanāyakayan*, the Principal of a Hindú Temple.
13. *Ṭen*—from *ṭhána* 'place' (Páli) is now obsolete. The modern form is *ten*, but this, in the sense of 'post' or 'office,' is more commonly written *ṭhánántara* or *tanatura*,
14. *Noek*—now more commonly written *noyek*.
15. Read *paṇḍita* for *paṇḍita*.
16. *Ruvanmēli*, more commonly called *Ruvanwēli*,—name of a celebrated Dágaba at Anurádhapura commenced by King Duṭṭugēmuṇu and completed by his brother Śeḍḍētissa. It is now known by the name of Rankot ('gold-pinnacled') Dágaba.
17. Read *svámīnta* for *suwámīnta*.
18. *Anun há asádháraṇa*,—lit: 'not common with others,' 'unlike others,' i. e., 'surpassing others.'
19. *Yála* = 1,280 kuruni; 1 kuruniya being equal to 4 ṇeli.
20. Reading *selesmeṭi* for *soḷosmaṭi*, where *seles* may be derived from the Páli *silesa* 'union,' and *maṭi* (modern *meṭi*) from *mattiká* 'clay,' hence 'adhesive clay.'
21. The *e* sound in *koṭe* is now replaced by *a*.
22. *Kalanda* = 60 grains (Apothecaries' weight.)

23. Reading *tunwana* for *tunpana*.
24. The Sinhalese paraphrase of the Attanagaluwaṅsa has *piyanasāva* for the Pāli *puppādhāna* which means 'a flower-receptacle' or 'floral seat.'
25. Literally: 'offerings of lamps of camphor in earthenware.'
26. Reading *dahas*, 'thousands' for s.
27. Read *un* for *unu*.
28. Read *wihārarakshāvé* for *wihāarakshāvé*.
29. *Samadaruvan* = *sāmidaruvan*, 'lords,' 'masters,' or 'overseers.'
30. *Pasakun*—'cooks' as being derived from *pāchaka* 'one who cooks' (P. and S.)
31. This is doubtful.
32. *Paḍeniye*,—the cavities between the circular rings of a *dāgaba*
33. *Pané* = modern *paná* 'combs': perhaps a kind of brush is meant here.
34. *Nahana*—(from the Pāli *nahānam*) means that which is applied, while bathing, to clean the person = the modern *nānu* 'unguents.'
35. *Ganun* = modern *gānarun* 'those who smear.'
36. *Mangul miṇḍiyan*,—this might also be rendered 'female servants employed on festive occasions.'
37. *Ruvanṃeli*—from *Ratnamāli*, another form of *Ruvanṃeli*.
38. *Thūpārāma*—the most ancient *dāgaba*, built by Dēwānanpiyatissa.
39. *Wasnētāt*—an archaism for *wasnāvuntāt*.
40. *Prétayanta*—'departed spirits doomed to suffer extreme misery.'
41. *Pet*—from the Pāli *patti* 'acquisition,' 'communication to others of the merit one has acquired,' when it is more commonly written *pattidāna*,
42. Read *tamaṅṭa* for *tamāta*.
43. Reading *pūjāvayi* for *pū*.....

No. 2.

INSCRIPTION AT PEPIĪYĀNA.

The copy of the Inscription from which the following translation has been made, is a transcript of another copy in the possession of L. De Soyza Mahā Mudaliyār, who courteously lent it to the translator. It is to be regretted that the Mahā Mudaliyār's health prevents him from completing the translation which he undertook some years back.

With a view to test the accuracy of the copy, the translator visited the temple-premises at Pepiṅiyāna, but, to his great disappointment, he found the stone in detached fragments built up into a wall, and the fragments themselves so much defaced that they could not be utilized for testing the style or spelling